

FUNCTIONALIZATION OF BASALT FIBRES BY HYDROTHERMAL GROWTH OF ZINC OXIDE NANOSTRUCTURES

Matteo Lilli*¹, Francesca Sbardella¹, Irene Bavasso¹, Maria P. Bracciale¹, Maria C. Seghini¹, Luca Di Palma¹, Jacopo Tirillò¹, Fabrizio Sarasini¹

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering Materials Environment, Sapienza-Università di Roma, Italy & UdR INSTM (National Interuniversity Consortium of Materials Science and Technology)

Email: matteo.lilli@uniroma1.it, francesca.sbardella@uniroma1.it, irene.bavasso@uniroma1.it, mariapaola.bracciale@uniroma1.it, mariacarolina.seghini@uniroma1.it, luca.dipalma@uniroma1.it, Jacopo.tirillo@uniroma1.it, Fabrizio.sarasini@uniroma1.it

Keywords: Basalt fibres, interfacial strength, ZnO nanowire, interphase.

ABSTRACT

This work aims at optimizing the decoration of basalt fibres with ZnO nanostructures as a function of growth time. Recently, the growth of ZnO nanorods on the surface of the fibres has been shown to have a significant influence on interfacial shear strength. The present work is based on the growth of ZnO nanorods on basalt fibres via low-temperature hydrothermal technique. Morphological and structural analyses by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) showed that the optimal uniformity and homogeneity of the ZnOs on the surface of the fibres were obtained for the reaction times of 6 h and 2 h for basalt fabrics and single basalt fibres, respectively. In parallel, single-fibre tensile tests have shown a slight decrease in the mechanical properties of basalt fibres due to the longer times of hydrothermal process. The wettability tests then dealt with the effect of the ZnO nanostructures on the wetting behavior of the basalt fabrics, highlighting a hydrophobic behavior, with contact angles between 125° and 130°.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced fibre composites have been widely used in structural applications due to their high specific strength and stiffness, outstanding corrosion resistance, and good design flexibility as compared with conventional structural metallic materials. In particular, the application of thermoplastic polymers as a matrix material in fibre reinforced composites has grown over the last decades due to recyclability issues. In fact, the adoption of stricter environmental regulations is stimulating the search for materials and products with the lowest possible environmental ‘footprint’ with a focus on renewable raw materials [1]. This enhanced awareness has triggered, especially in Europe, a shift towards using natural materials as a substitute for non-renewable synthetic fibres like glass or carbon in composites based on both thermosetting and thermoplastic polymers. Currently, glass fibres cover about 90% of the market of fibre-reinforced composite materials and at the end of their life they are traditionally directed to landfills. This happens because the recycling operations of these materials are difficult and very expensive. For these reasons, with the aim of reducing the environmental impact, there is a growing interest in the use of natural fibres as reinforcement in polymer composites [2]. In recent years, many types of natural fibres have been studied and considered as reinforcing materials for polymeric matrices. Flax, jute, kenaf and sisal fibres have shown lower tensile strength and Young's modulus compared to synthetic fibres, therefore it can be inconvenient their use even in semi-structural applications. Indeed, in terms of geometry, natural fibres are not uniform monofilament cylinders like carbon and glass, but bundles of elementary fibres which consist of voids and defects with irregular cross-sections. Moreover, a further drawback is the chemical incompatibility with many hydrophobic polymeric matrices, which involves a poor interfacial adhesion and a limited stress transfer efficiency. Among natural fibres, quite recently basalt fibre has been proposed as a potential competitor to the widely used glass fibre [3]. It has been referred to as a ‘natural’ fibre as its singular raw material, basalt (an extrusive igneous (volcanic) rock), does not require synthesis in the way that traditional glass fibre formulations do. Basalt is an eco-

sustainable material, characterized by excellent resistance to chemical agents, excellent acoustic insulation properties and excellent resistance to high and low temperatures. In fact, basalt fibres can be used from temperatures around -200 °C up to 600-800 °C. In terms of mechanical performance, the single fibre strength and Young's modulus are stated as at least comparable with commonly used E-glass fibres: the modulus, in particular, is often quoted as approaching 90 GPa which is significantly higher than E-glass fibres with about 80 GPa [3]–[5] (table 1).

	Basalt	E-Glass
Density (g/cm ³)	2.8	2.56
Elastic modulus (GPa)	89	76
Tensile strength (GPa)	2.8	1.4-2.5
Elongation to fracture (%)	3.15	1.8-3.2
Specific E modulus (GPa per g/cm ³)	31.78	30
Specific tensile strength (GPa per g/cm ³)	1	0.5-1

Table 1: Mechanical properties of basalt and E-glass fibres [3].

It is well known that mechanical and physical properties of a fibrous composite are not only dictated by the properties of the single constituents (strong fibres and a suitable matrix do not necessarily form an equally performing composite material), but also by fibre/matrix interphase. In fact, the mechanical properties of the final composite material are strictly controlled by the fibre/matrix interface [6][7]. In this regard, all reinforcing fibres used for manufacturing polymer composites are surface treated and/or coated, usually during their manufacturing steps, which are usually referred to as “sizing”. Fibre sizing is a fundamental stage during the manufacture of fibres and hence remains one of the simplest and most cost-effective methods for promoting adhesion. Sizing is a multi-purpose coating which accounts for 0.2-5% of the fibre weight but, due to the nature of application, is frequently non-uniform. The sizing consists of an adhesion promoter (usually an organosilane compound as coupling agent) a film former along with a suitable emulsifier and a lubricant which have protective functions during production and handling [8], [9]. This wet chemical process of sizing application shows several significant drawbacks: the resulting coating is not of a consistent thickness and uniformity, much of the sizing used on basalt fibres is inherited from glass fibre technology (thus being not necessarily optimised for basalt fibres [10]), the molecules of silane coupling agents are often prone to self-condense, forming siloxane oligomers rather than a complete bonding with the fibre surface [11] and, most notably, only a limited fraction (in the range 10–20%) of the total sizing is bonded to the fibre surface [12]. In recent years, the formation of hierarchical structures or whiskers has been developed in order to modify the surface of the fibres, creating mechanical interlocks and/or local stiffening at the fibre/matrix interface, which can improve stress transfer and interfacial properties. For this purpose, Sodano et al. have developed an alternative whiskerization process, aimed at the growth of ZnO nanowires on the surface of carbon fibres, leading to a 110 % increase in interfacial resistance [13]. Nowadays, the challenge is to control the growth mechanisms of these crystalline nanostructures, thus achieving precise shapes and sizes. Many methods, such as the metalorganic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD), the electrochemical deposition technique, the sputter deposition technique or the pulse laser deposition method have been used for the synthesis of ZnO nanowires [14]. However, all these techniques require very severe

operating conditions, such as high temperature and accurate concentrations of gaseous phases, and for these reasons they are not suitable for the surface modification of the fibres. Unlike the above-mentioned high temperature processes, the method developed by Sodano et al. allows the growth of ZnO in aqueous solutions with the use of low temperatures, thus preserving the mechanical properties of the original fibres [15]. Subsequently, numerous studies on this hydrothermal process have been carried out, above all with regard to carbon and glass fibres. Less attention has been paid to basalt fibres, due to their recent introduction into the composites market. The aim of the present work is to study the effects of the number of seeding cycles and growth times on the decoration process of basalt fibres with ZnO nanostructures with a view to improving the interfacial properties with polymer matrices.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Raw materials

The nanostructure growth processes have been carried out on two different substrates. Basalt fibres without sizing were provided by Mafic as a continuous roving with a nominal diameter of 13 μm and a linear density of 450 tex. The second material used is a commercial plain woven basalt fabric (220 g/m^2) supplied by Basaltex, with a commercial sizing compatible with epoxy resin.

2.2 Synthesis of ZnO nanostructures

Starting from a seed layer of ZnO nanoparticles deposited on the surface of the basalt fibres it was possible to grow the ZnO nanowires [16]. For the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticle seeds, 1 mmol of zinc acetate dihydrate (Sigma–Aldrich, 99 %) was dissolved in 80 mL of ethanol (VWR Chemicals, > 99.8 %) at 50 °C and vigorously stirred for 5 min. A separate solution of 2 mM sodium hydroxide (Sigma–Aldrich, 97%) was dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol at 50 °C and stirred vigorously for 5 min. Both solutions were then cooled to room temperature. Upon cooling, 40 mL of zinc acetate solution was added to 320 mL of ethanol, and 40 mL of sodium hydroxide solution was added to 100 mL of ethanol. The solutions were heated separately to 65 °C then mixed together under vigorous stirring while maintaining the temperature at 65 °C for 30 min. The unsized fibres and the fabrics were rinsed with ethanol and dried at 150 °C for 10 minutes. The ZnO nanoparticle seeds were coated on the fibres by dipping them into the solution and then annealing the fibres at 150 °C for 10 min. For the ZnO nanowire growth process, 3.71 g of zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Sigma–Aldrich, 99%) and 1.75 g of hexamethylenetetramine (Sigma–Aldrich) were dissolved in 500 mL of 18 M Ω cm Milli-Q water and heated to 90 °C under vigorous stirring. Once the solution reached 90 °C, the fibres were immersed in the beaker containing the growth solution. A sample was taken to characterize the morphologies at different growth times, from 2 to 6 hours for the basalt fabrics and from 60 to 120 min for the single basalt fibres. At the end of the process, in order to remove the solution residues, the fibres were rinsed with distilled water and finally dried at room temperature.

2.3 Single fibre tensile testing

The mechanical properties of the single basalt fibres have been evaluated following the ASTM C1557 standard. The tensile tests were performed at room temperature with a Zwick / Roell Z010 equipped with a 100 N load cell. Tests were performed in displacement control at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. At least 30 single basalt fibres for each type of ZnO deposition have been tested, choosing three different gauge lengths (20, 30 and 40 mm). After placing and gluing the fibres onto the paper supports, the diameters were measured using an optical microscope Nikon Eclipse 150L equipped with the image analysis software Lucia Measurement. The actual specimen elongation in the gauge length was determined by subtracting the displacement associated with the system compliance from the total cross-head displacement. The system compliance was measured according to ASTM C1557 by obtaining the force versus displacement behavior of the fibres at three gauge lengths, namely 20 mm, 30 mm and 40 mm. Through a two-parameter Weibull distribution the scatter of the Young's modulus and tensile strength were evaluated using the equation (1):

$$F(X) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{X}{X_0} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (1)$$

$F(X)$ is the probability of failure of the parameter X , α is the Weibull modulus and X_0 represents a scale parameter. The probability of failure is measured using the following equation (2):

$$F_j = \frac{j-0.5}{N} \quad (2)$$

N is the number of tested fibres and j is the rank of the j th data point. A single set of parameters for each property (tensile strength or Young's modulus), X_0 and α , was obtained from the intercept and slope, respectively, of the plot $\ln\{\ln[1/(1-F)]\}$ against $\ln(X)$ [17].

2.4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Basalt fibre morphology after ZnO growth was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (Tescan MIRA3). All samples were sputter coated with chromium before being analyzed.

2.5 Static contact angle

The wetting properties of modified basalt fibres were investigated by measuring the static contact angle with a video-based optical contact angle measuring instrument, OCA 15 Pro. During this test, degassed water drops with a volume of 4 μ l were applied to the basalt fabric.

2.6 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) was performed at room temperature to identify the crystalline phases present on the surfaces of the basalt fibres subjected to the ZnO nanowires growth process. X-ray diffraction (Philips X'Pert Pro) spectra were collected in a step-scan mode in the 2θ range from 10° to 80° with a step width of 0.01° and a counting time of 7 s per step. The employed radiation was monochromated $\text{Cu}_{k\alpha}$ (40 kV – 40 mA).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The immersion time of the basalt fibres inside the growth solution plays a significant role in the control of the different morphologies obtainable for the ZnO nanostructures [16]. After a first preparation step, using ethanol, the seeds of the zinc oxides were deposited on the surfaces of the basalt fibres through a seeding process. The fibres were only subjected to a single seeding cycle and a subsequent removal of the solution residues inside an oven at a temperature of 150°C . Therefore, to evaluate the influence of the growth time on the uniformity and on the diameter of the ZnOs, the nanowires growth process was conducted for different times, keeping constant the concentrations of the chemical agents used. The first chemical treatments were performed on basalt fabrics for four different growth times: 2, 3, 4 and 6 hours. It is important to highlight that the growth solutions have been refreshed every hour, up to a maximum of 5 times for the 6-hour growth process. Subsequently, an XRD analysis was performed to evaluate the presence of crystal structures on the surface of the fibres. From Fig. 1 it is possible to highlight the high intensity of the crystalline phase peaks of the curve at 6 hours, corresponding to the hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO, which shows an increasing yield of the process with increasing time [18].

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction spectra for basalt fabrics as a function of ZnO growth time.

The presence of nanostructures and their different morphologies were also confirmed and analysed by scanning electron microscopy (Fig. 2). The zinc oxides of the basalt fabric subjected to a 2-hour growth treatment show many different shapes and from their small size it can be understood that their growth process has not reached the maximum yield. For the 3 and 4 hours processes, as for the previous ones, the hexagonal nanostructures are characterized by small dimensions, but the basalt fibre fabrics show much more uniform surfaces, even if not completely covered by the nanowires. As in the case of X-ray analysis, the best results were obtained with 6-hour growth, thanks to the presence of well-formed zinc oxides on all the fibres of the processed fabric.

Figure 2: Basalt fibre fabrics with ZnO nanowires (a) after a 2 hour growth process, (b) after a 3 hour growth process, (c) after a 4 hour growth process, (d) after a 6 hour growth process.

These morphologies led to different wetting properties. In fact, while the virgin fabric appeared to be hydrophilic, when modified by the presence of the ZnO showed a hydrophobic behavior (Fig. 3). Table 2 shows the results of the static contact angle analysis for basalt fabrics subjected to treatments ranging from 3 to 6 hours. It is important to underline how the contact angles reach very high values after growth treatments, showing behaviours close to the super hydrophobic, with angles between 125 and 131 degrees.

Figure 3: Water drop test analysis (a) after a 3-hour growth process, (b) after a 4-hour growth process, (c) after a 6-hour growth process.

Basalt fabric	$\Theta_{\text{WATER}} (^{\circ})$
After 3h growth	131.82 ± 6.9
After 4h growth	127.54 ± 4.8
After 6h growth	125.28 ± 12.8

Table 2: Static contact angle obtained from measurements on basalt fibre fabrics.

The second part of the work was based on the application of the same growth processes of ZnOs on single basalt fibres without surface sizing. The first surface treatments were conducted for shorter times, from 60 to 120 min, evaluating at the same time how these surface modifications influenced the mechanical properties of the fibres. As with fabrics, the growth solutions have been refreshed, but this time every 30 min. Table 3 shows the results obtained for fibre strength after treatments at 60, 90 and 120 min. For these preliminary tests a single 20 mm gauge length was used.

Basalt fibres	Tensile strength (MPa)
As received	2207.11 ± 548.75
After 60 min growth	1915.18 ± 428.31
After 90 min growth	1796.44 ± 456.82
After 120 min growth	1696.44 ± 187.20

Table 3: Tensile properties of single basalt fibres.

The growth time was found to adversely affect the mechanical properties of the fibres, thus suggesting to limit the growth time at 2 h. A subsequent morphological study was conducted using a scanning electron microscope (Fig. 4-7). From micrographs, it is possible to note that the zinc oxides obtained on basalt fibres treated for 60 and 90 min are characterized by reduced dimensions in length and diameters. Thus, this incomplete development of the nanostructures led to a superficial non-homogeneity of the fibres, and an agglomeration of the single oxides. A remarkable difference was found for the treatment of 120 min. In fact, the nanostructures obtained show considerably increased dimensions. Furthermore, better results have been obtained about the homogeneity and uniformity of the surface of the basalt bundles subjected to the treatments. This trend does not follow that shown by the basalt fabric, thus suggesting the existence of a strong dependence on the solid to liquid ratio used during the growth step.

Figure 4: Virgin basalt fibres without surface sizing.

Figure 5: Unsized basalt fibres with ZnO nanowires after a 60 min growth process.

Figure 6: Unsized basalt fibres with ZnO nanowires after a 90 min growth process.

Figure 5: Unsized basalt fibres with ZnO nanowires after a 120 min growth process.

For this reason, our research work was focused on the 120 min growth process. A more specific analysis of the mechanical properties of basalt fibres subjected to this chemical treatment was performed, using three different gauge lengths (20, 30 and 40 mm) and the two parameters Weibull distribution, for virgin and treated fibres. In Tables 4 and 5 are reported the results from the tensile tests as well as the values of the characteristic parameters of the Weibull distribution of the untreated fibres, while the results related to the fibres subjected to 2-hour growth are shown in Tables 6 and 7.

Gauge length (mm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)
20	2207.11 ± 548.75	91.92 ± 11.63
30	1763.88 ± 545.05	98.50 ± 7.78
40	1535.61 ± 438.64	96.33 ± 8.27

Table 4: Tensile properties of untreated fibres.

Gauge length (mm)	Tensile strength $-\alpha_{\sigma}$	Tensile strength (MPa) $-\sigma_0$	Young's modulus $-\alpha_E$	Young's modulus (GPa) $-E_0$
20	4.82	2481.41	12.37	97.91
30	4.26	1981.51	20.35	100.23
40	4.76	1747.63	18.24	97.82

Table 5: Weibull distribution parameters for untreated basalt fibres.

Gauge length (mm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)
20	1696.44 ± 187.20	98.91 ± 8.87
30	1654.19 ± 204.46	91.97 ± 12.39
40	1617.26 ± 206.53	97.57 ± 12.68

Table 6: Tensile properties of fibres subjected to a 2-hour growth process.

Gauge length (mm)	Tensile strength $-\alpha_\sigma$	Tensile strength $-\sigma_0$	Young's modulus $-\alpha_E$	Young's modulus $-E_0$
20	10.21	1782.39	4.14	112.95
30	9.11	1746.38	3.55	106.78
40	8.44	1697.48	2.85	117.99

Table 7: Weibull distribution parameters for fibres subjected to a 2-hour growth process.

Finally, by plotting the Young's modulus and strength as a function of the three different gauge lengths (20, 30 and 40 mm), a linear trend of the Weibull distribution was obtained, confirming the validity of a unimodal Weibull function (Fig. 6). These results confirmed the slight decrease in the tensile strength of the treated fibres.

Figure 6: Weibull plots of single fibre strength and Young's modulus for basalt fibres with ZnO nanowires after a 120 min growth process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The surface modification treatment proved to be effective for basalt fabrics and for single fibres. In particular, in this work the growth time was checked to obtain optimized dimensions for the ZnO nanowires and a uniform and homogeneous coverage of the treated fibres. In the case of basalt fabrics, an XRD analysis showed that increasing the process time resulted in an increase in the amount of nanostructures on the fibre surfaces. This result was also confirmed by a morphological analysis using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), which also showed that the best shapes and sizes of the ZnOs were obtained with the 6-hour growth time. Finally, this chemical modification has led basalt fabrics to exhibit behaviour at the limit of super hydrophobicity. Unlike basalt fabrics, the optimization of the growth process for single unsized fibres was already achieved for a time of 2 hours, as confirmed by a morphological analysis. At the same time, tensile testing was used to evaluate the effect of chemical

treatment on the mechanical properties of fibres. Compared to the untreated fibres, a reduction in tensile strength of about 13 % was found for the 2-hour process, and for this reason it was decided not to increase the process times further. This difference in results for the two types of materials led to the hypothesis of the existence of a strong relationship between the amount of material (single fibres or fabrics) treated and the volume of the chemical agents in the growth solutions. In conclusion, this structural modification of the basalt fibres opens up new and promising perspectives for the improvement of the interfacial fibre / matrix adhesion compared to the methods already widely used, such as surface oxidation or the use of new sizing formulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. Faruk, A. K. Bledzki, H.-P. Fink, and M. Sain, "Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibres: 2000–2010," *Prog. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1552–1596, Nov. 2012.
- [2] K. L. Pickering, M. G. A. Efendy, and T. M. Le, "A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 83, pp. 98–112, 2016.
- [3] V. Fiore, T. Scalici, G. Di Bella, and A. Valenza, "A review on basalt fibre and its composites," *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 74, pp. 74–94, 2015.
- [4] F. Sarasini, J. Tirillò, and M. C. Seghini, "Influence of thermal conditioning on tensile behavior of single basalt fibres," *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 132, pp. 77–86, 2018.
- [5] J. Li, H. Richards, C., & Watson, "High-Performance Glass Fibre Development for Composite Applications," *Int. J. Appl. Glas. Sci.*, vol. 5, pp. 65–81, 2014.
- [6] J. Karger-Kocsis, H. Mahmood, and A. Pegoretti, "Recent advances in fibre/matrix interphase engineering for polymer composites," *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 73, pp. 1–43, 2015.
- [7] M. W. Hyer, "*Stress analysis of fibre-reinforced composite materials*." DEStech Publ. Inc.
- [8] J. . Thomason and L. . Adzima, "Sizing up the interphase: an insider's guide to the science of sizing," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 32, no. 3–4, pp. 313–321, Mar. 2001.
- [9] M. Dey, J. M. Deitzel, J. W. Gillespie, and S. Schweiger, "Influence of sizing formulations on glass/epoxy interphase properties," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 63, pp. 59–67, Aug. 2014.
- [10] P. G. Jenkins, L. Yang, and Thomason, "Investigation of the effect of sizing on the tensile and interface properties of continuous basalt fibre and polypropylene," in *18th European Conference on Composite Materials, 2018*.
- [11] G. . Nishioka, "Interaction of organosilanes with glass fibers," *J. Non. Cryst. Solids*, vol. 120, no. 1–3, pp. 102–107, Apr. 1990.
- [12] J. L. Thomason, "The interface region in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy resin composites: 3. Characterization of fibre surface coatings and the interphase," *Composites*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 487–498, Jul. 1995.
- [13] H. A. Sodano, Y. Lin, G. Ehlert, "Increased interface strength in carbon fibre composites through a ZnO nanowire interphase," *Adv Funct Mater*, Vol. 19, Issue16, pp. 2654-2660, 2009.
- [14] G. Amin, M. H. Asif, A. Zainelabdin, S. Zaman, O. Nur, M. Willander, "Influence of pH, precursor concentration, growth time, and temperature on the morphology of ZnO nanostructures grown by Hydrothermal method" *Journal of Nanomaterials*, Volume 2011, Article ID 269692, 9 pages.
- [15] B. Wang, Y. Duan, and J. Zhang, "Applied Surface Science A controllable interface performance through varying ZnO nanowires dimensions on the carbon fibres," *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, vol. 389, pp. 96–102, 2016.
- [16] U. Galan, Y. Lin, G. J. Ehlert, and H. A. Sodano, "Effect of ZnO nanowire morphology on the interfacial strength of nanowire coated carbon fibres," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 71, no. 7, pp. 946–954, 2011.
- [17] J. D. Sullivan and P. H. Lauzon, Experimental probability estimators for Weibull plots, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 1245–1247, 1986.
- [18] B. Cheng, E. T. Samulski, Hydrothermal synthesis of one-dimensional ZnO nanostructures with different aspect ratios, *Chem. Commun.*, 2004, pp.986-987.